

Reality Check on Official Codification and Practice of Broadcast Professionalisation in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined how the National Broadcasting Commission (NBC) constructs broadcast professionalisation in Nigeria through the Sixth Edition of the Nigeria Broadcasting Code (2019). Anchored on Authoritarian Press and System of Professions theories, the study adopted Qualitative Document Analysis and applied (Ready, Extract, Analyse and Distil), READ procedure to interrogate profession-related clauses in the Code. Findings revealed that the Code frames broadcasting as a specialised profession requiring structured training, continuous capacity development, ethical judgement, verification, and adherence to codified professional standards. However, a major internal contradiction is evident. While the Code prescribes rigorous professional expectations, it simultaneously permits entry into broadcasting with an Ordinary National Diploma (OND). It also allows untrained individuals with “proven aptitude” to practise broadcasting prior to formal training. This regulatory inconsistency undermines broadcast professional identity, weakens competence and ethical performance, and constrains effective self-regulation within the industry. The study concluded that broadcast professionalisation in Nigeria remains largely aspirational due to the misalignment between entry requirements and prescribed professional competencies. The study therefore, recommended raising the entry thresholds of people into broadcasting to a university degree certificate. It equally recommended the abolition of aptitude-based practice, enforcement of mandatory pre-practice professional training, and strengthening continuous professional development to support a coherent and sustainable professional broadcast system in Nigeria.

Keywords: Broadcast Professionalisation, Nigeria Broadcasting Code, the NBC, Systems of Profession Theory

Introduction

Broadcasting rests on the interplay of foundational knowledge, aptitude and ethics, yet, this triad of professionalisation is characterised by challenges in the Nigerian broadcast industry (Jolaoso, Roleola & Kuserki, 2025). Although the Nigeria Broadcasting Code (NBC, 2019) positions broadcasting as a profession anchored in competence and ethical responsibility, but the entry requirements it prescribes indicate that broadcasting still falls

below the status of a full profession in Nigeria. This regulatory gap permits the entry of untrained individuals, whose unprofessional conduct continuously undermines broadcast practice in the country (Elendu-Obochi, Okon & Njoku, 2025). Through the regulatory lacuna of the NBC, individuals who dabbled into broadcast practice without foundational knowledge now claim openly that a university degree in broadcast journalism or Mass Communication is unnecessary for effective and ethical practice of broadcasting. Antithetically, studies carried out by scholars like Adams & Sharu (2024), and Badiora & Sanusi, (2024) affirm the indispensability of formal training not only for broadcast professionalism practice, but for every standard profession.

The perception of such dabblers, though officially supported by the NBC, has encouraged a steady rise in underqualified entrants in broadcast roles, who parade themselves as anchors, presenters, producers, and reporters on Nigerian radio and television stations. Scholars refute this problematic trend and assert that it weakens the professional identity of the industry, thereby accelerating it to deprofessionalisation (Eke, Adeyemi & Ochor, 2024). Guided by this concern, the study therefore aims to examine how the NBC frames broadcast professionalisation in its Code, identify contradictions between its professionalisation claims and its entry provisions and assess how these inconsistencies shape competence, ethics, and the professional development of the Nigerian broadcast workforce

Statement of the Problem

The way by which the National Broadcasting Commission (NBC, 2019), has framed the professionalisation of broadcasting in Nigeria is not only ambiguous but contradictory. The Commission, in its Code, describes broadcasting as a creative medium which is characterised by professionalism. To under this better, scholars conceptualise a profession as a field requiring advanced knowledge that supports adherence to professional standards (Trathen, Scambler & Gallagher, 2023). However, despite this clear cognitive standardisation, the NBC, having acknowledged broadcasting as a profession, ironically allows individuals whose qualifications fall below the threshold expected of a standard profession to practise broadcasting just because of their proven aptitude. This concession granted by the Commission is part of the major challenges militating against broadcast professionalisation in the country.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. How does the NBC define and frame broadcast professionalisation in the Nigeria Broadcasting Code?
2. What contradictions exist between the NBC's professionalisation claims and its entry provisions for broadcast practitioners?
3. How do these contradictions affect competence, ethics and the professional development of Nigeria's broadcast workforce?

Conceptual Foundations on Professionalisation

A profession is typically anchored in specialised knowledge, structured learning and ethical regulation (Robbins & O'Connor, 2023); while a professional is one who embodies the aforementioned by demonstrating competence and accountability (Almashaqbeh, Alshurafat & Al Amosh, 2023). Thus, professionalisation elevates an occupation to the status of a profession through formalised certification and internal regulatory authority. Although its implementation, Postema, (2024) admits, often exposes gaps between regulatory policies and practical realities. As for professionalism, it is the behavioural test of professionalisation claim. This is because professionalism reveals the ethical conduct of practitioners in their daily activities (Hanifi & Gheiasi, 2024).

Broadcasting operates as a civic institution that shapes public knowledge, culture, and democratic engagement. Hence, it demands standards that go beyond technical proficiency. Scholars posit that professionalism rests on the triad of competence, ethics, and regulation (Oso, Adeniran & Arowolo (2024). When any of these pillars falter, ethical lapses and operational disorder surface in the work of practitioners. The weight of these obligations underscores the necessity of structured preparation for broadcast practice in Nigeria (Elendu-Obochi, Okon, & Njoku, 2025).

Furthermore, professions depend on codified bodies of knowledge that enable consistent and credible performance (Syrigou & Williams, 2023). In broadcasting, this encompasses media law, ethics, news judgement, and technical processes that collectively ensure reliable output. Adams & Sharu (2024) establish that structured training is indispensable in broadcast practice. Similarly, Pajnik (2023) observes that domain-specific expertise remains a global prerequisite for meaningful professional contribution. The position of these scholars is further substantiated by Egere & Ushie (2024). They argue that creativity or aptitude, as approved by the NBC (2019) may enhance vocal delivery of broadcast content but cannot substitute competence grounded in formal preparation for this audiovisual field. These scholarly insights, therefore, reinforce the fact that effective broadcasting in Nigeria demands both cognitive and technical readiness from practitioners.

Global Pressures on Professional Identity

In alignment with earlier cited studies, Fraser (2023) distinguishes professionalisation as institutional development from professionalism that is behavioural expression. He sees that weak institutional systems often constrain ethical performance. Additionally, Fai, Bayighomog & Stubbs (2024) observe that heightened demands for audience engagement have broadened required competencies but blurred boundaries between entertainment and professional judgement. In the African media context, professional performance is constrained by newsroom infrastructures, data capacity and institutional ecosystems that influence how journalists gather, verify, and present information (Chiumbu & Munoriyarwa, 2023). Even as stations compete for ratings, audiences still expect accuracy and responsibility from them. Therefore, institutional accreditation remains

essential for sustaining ethical norms (Örnebring, 2024), These global dynamics reflect the challenges confronting professionalisation of the Nigerian broadcast system.

NBC Position on Broadcast Professionalisation

The NBC (2019) defines broadcasting as a creative medium characterised by professionalism. As a profession, the Code outlines six objectives that broadcasting in Nigeria strives to achieve in line with the national communication policies. These objectives are embedded in most PESTEL concepts (political, economic, social, technological, cultural and professional). Thus, actualisation of these objectives, as set by the NBC, requires cognitively competent and ethically grounded broadcast practitioners. Ironically, the Code stipulates a qualification lower than what is expected of a standard profession. The Code states that:

The minimum entry requirement of a Broadcaster shall be an Ordinary Diploma or a Certificate from a recognised Media Training Institution,' (NBC, 2019, p. 33).

This leniency of the NBC conflicts with its claim of positioning broadcasting as a profession in Nigeria. Thus, another section of the Code states that:

Nigerian broadcasting shall essentially match the best in the profession anywhere in the world. for global-standard broadcasting, (NBC, 2019, p. 12).

The tension between regulatory aspiration and permissive entry rules creates a structural contradiction that militates against broadcast professionalisation in Nigeria. Worse still, the Code also permits individuals who are entirely untrained to practise broadcasting based on their vocal abilities. Thus, the Code states that:

The Broadcaster shall ensure that newly recruited staff with proven aptitude but without industry experience attend a relevant course at a recognised broadcast institution within two years of employment (p. 34).

The section above clearly indicates that broadcasting is not a profession, as the NBC positions it in its Code, but an all-comers affair that every Tom, Dick and Harry can dabble into and practise it based supposed aptitude.

Proven Aptitude versus Professionalism

Studies indicate a steady erosion of professional values in the Nigerian broadcast industry due to the NBC regulatory lacuna. The consequentiality, as Matthews & Onyemaobi (2020) observe, is that untrained people with no formal training in Mass Communication continuously dabble into broadcast journalism practice. Such individuals often prioritise commercialisation of their broadcast journalism practice over professionalism (Inobemhe, Modeyin & Ugber, 2025). This has resulted in persistent decline of broadcast values (Okon, Aruku, Agbo & Udoyo, 2025; Shehu, 2017). In contrast, however, well

trained broadcasters exhibit stronger ethical discipline in their broadcast journalism practice (Banjo & Oduwobi, 2023; Enesi, Ibrahim & Salami, 2025).

As the debate over broadcast professionalisation and cognitive grounding in broadcasting continues, some broadcast practitioners who dabbled into it with no initial cognitive backing claim that broadcast journalism practice requires no formal education. For example, Rufai Oseni of Arise News substantiated this claim. He wrote and shared on his X (formerly Twitter) handle, a list of journalists in Nigeria and around the world who studied courses different from Mass Communication in universities, dabbled into journalism practice and eventually became successful. To those who argued in favour of this claim, as approved by the NBC, aptitude endowed in such untrained broadcast practitioners suffices for professional broadcast practice.

While this claim may be valid to a certain extent, given the potential alignment between the aptitude of individuals and journalism practice, scholars add that genuine success in any field of specialisation requires a strong passion for, or interest in the chosen field, access to competent institutions and qualified lecturers who can train the learner until he becomes cognitively and professionally grounded, and, most importantly, alignment between the natural abilities of a person and the field of study, as earlier noted (Wild & Kunina-Habenicht, 2025).

However, regarding the alignment of natural abilities with journalism practice, Banning (2016) emphatically cautions that communicative abilities alone are insufficient for journalism work. He argues that relying solely on aptitude to practise broadcasting, as is permissible under the NBC (2019) framework, poses potential risks to society. Banning further contends that journalism practitioners who studied disciplines different from Mass Communication or Journalism and later became successful in the profession are, in fact, failures in their original callings. His point is that such people may have wasted their valuable time and resources studying fields that were not perhaps, aligned with their innate talents, and for which they lacked passion for, nor had genuine interest in. Consequently, Banning suggests that if they had studied Mass Communication, as common sense would indicate, they might have been even more successful in journalism practice.

Despite some people's dismissal of the need for relevant knowledge acquisition prior to practising broadcast journalism, evidence of inadequate cognitive grounding can be observed in the on-air conduct of many untrained broadcast practitioners. It is on this reason that critics frequently accuse Oseni of turning interview programmes he anchors into hostile interrogations, which, in some instances, escalate into personal confrontations between him and his guests. Also, they observe that his choice of words often falls below the standards expected in broadcast language. For instance, during a live interview, Olalere Olayinka, Senior Special Adviser on Public Communications and Social Media to the FCT Minister, Nyesom Wike, reprimanded the Arise News anchor for using an inappropriate phrase ("you guys") in reference to officials of the Federal Capital Development Authority (FCDA). Although Oseni refused to acknowledge the error and

accept Olayinka's correction, the response of the Arise News anchor, many observed, contained elements of broadcast professional ignorance (Bolawole, 2025).

Beyond this individual case, politics, as it is commonly described, is a dirty game. In this respect, Popoola (2023) likens the media to the field on which politicians play this game, while journalists serve as referees and linesmen. To advance their selfish interests, politicians prefer this field on which they play their dirty game to be rough. The expression here is a metaphor for poorly regulated broadcasting staffed by untrained or inadequately trained broadcasters. Thus, scholars caution that unbaked or half-baked broadcasters are easily manipulated by political actors. Similarly, inadequate cognitive grounding militates against ethical independence in broadcast practice (Musa & Antwi-Boateng, 2023). Consequently, while cognitively unprepared journalists assume to practise watchdog journalism in their interview programmes by engaging in hostile confrontations with their guests, many of whom are politicians, they are, in reality, being manipulated by those same politicians to advance their selfish political interests.

Therefore, the menace of granting untrained individuals access to studios to practise broadcasting does not only bring more regulatory stress to the NBC, as netizens are being stressed due to unregulated content on social media (Ibe, Chinemerem, & Chibunma, 2024), it can, in fact, be as harmful as placing weapons of mass destruction (WMDs) in the hands of unskilled fighters. Such a situation can lead to devastating consequences (Nigussie, Kiflu, & Desta, 2024). The Rwandan genocide illustrates this stark reality. Historical records show that untrained individuals who gained access to radio stations took to the microphones and disseminated hate speech among Rwandan citizens. This unprofessional conduct contributed substantially to the civil war that claimed the lives of nearly one million Rwandans (Hefti & Jonas, 2020).

In order not to expose themselves to the wrath of the state, which hunts journalists for minor errors committed in the cause of doing their duty, or ignite Nigerian society into flames, as a result of spreading hate speech, Ogwezzy-Ndisika, Hussein, Faustino & Ejiwunmi (2021) recommend that media practitioners should perform their duties by strictly adhering to the principles and ethics of journalism profession. But their compliance with rules and regulations is only possible when they are aware of these regulations, which are embedded in professional knowledge and ethics. This, as Adams & Sharu (2024) reiterate in their studies on mass media and professionalism in Nigeria radio and television, is what makes acquisition of formal journalism knowledge or training absolutely necessary.

Broadcast Professionalisation from Multidisciplinary Approach

Despite ongoing debates about the professional status of broadcast journalism, audiences still expect accuracy and ethical judgement from broadcasters (Banjac, Juarez Miro & Hanusch, 2024). Ethical reporting remains central to sustaining public trust, especially in societies like Nigeria with fragile institutions (Tayo-Garbson, Odionyenma, Okoro, Etenge-Martins & Nnorom, 2024). However, weak regulatory enforcement by the NBC limits the ability of the sector to meet these expectations. Such regulatory weakness in

fragile media environments exacerbates threats to professional efficiency, safety and ethical practice, leaving journalists vulnerable to institutional pressure and compromised standards (Okafor & Onyenekwe, 2020). Undoubtedly, the low entry requirements approved by Nigeria Broadcasting Code (2019) further accelerate the deprofessionalisation of broadcasting in the country. With these regulatory provisions, Nigerian radio and television stations prioritise performance traits over cognitive competence.

The International Centre for Investigative Reporting (ICIR) observes that many journalists in Nigeria lack adequate literacy in budgets and procurement processes. According to the centre, this cognitive deficit limits the watchdog role of journalists in reporting and holding public officials to account (Akinwale, 2018). In response to the deficit, Mass Communication was unbundled; hence, new courses are now being taught to empower undergraduate students to be more professional in the labour market. For instance, Faculty of Communication and Media University of Lagos, offers a course called: “Reporting the Economy” to build students’ competence in financial reporting (Bin Hyacinth & Ibraheem, 2024). Extending this interdisciplinary shift, Bin Hyacinth and Ibraheem (2024) propose a dual-profession model for journalism profession. Their model acknowledges that professionals like medical doctors, economists, lawyers, psychologists, engineers, can significantly enrich journalism practice through expertise from their primary fields. They stipulated, as a condition, that such people from different backgrounds, must undergo formal journalism training. When successfully trained, they may operate as specialised broadcasters or “subject-matter journalists.” Thus, they bear designations like medical journalists, financial journalists, or legal correspondents. In this way, journalism adopts an approach of multidisciplinary knowledge while maintaining its ethical and professional boundaries (Bin Hyacinth & Ibraheem, 2024).

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the authoritarian press and the system of professions theories. The authoritarian press theory asserts that the state fully controls the operations of the press (Pearson, 2024), a perspective that aligns with objective two of this paper. In this regard, the NBC, as an instrument of the state, claims to promote broadcast professionalisation. But as part of its control of the Nigerian broadcast sector, the Commission contradicts its claim by reducing broadcasting below the status of a standard profession through its permissive entry of unqualified individuals into it.

Second, the System of Professions theory posits that professions secure and defend jurisdiction only when their expertise, training, regulation and institutional legitimacy operate as a coherent system (Kronblad & Jensen, 2023). This aligns with objectives one and three of this study. It further demonstrates that the low entry requirements of the NBC disrupt the jurisdictional coherence of broadcasting in Nigeria, thereby weakening its capacity to develop into a stable and fully professional field in the country.

Methodology

This study adopted Qualitative Document Analysis (QDA) to examine how the NBC, (2019) constructs broadcast professionalisation and entry requirements. The Code was obtained from publicly available official sources, and profession-related clauses constituted the unit of analysis. Using the Ready, Extract, Analyse and Distil (READ) procedure, these clauses were systematically extracted and deductively coded (Dalglish, Khalid & McMahon, 2020). Analysis was informed by professionalisation literature and guided by the Authoritarian Press and System of Professions theories in interpreting issues of expertise, regulation, and state control (Cairney, 2023; Kronblad & Jensen, 2023; Pearson, 2024). As the study relied solely on a public regulatory document, ethical approval was not required.

Extraction Matrix of Profession-Related Clauses in the NBC (2019) Code

Summary of the NBC provisions containing “profession,” “professional,” “professionalism” or related constructions, alongside assigned analytical codes.

NBC Clause (2019)	Extracted Professional Wording	Code	Interpretation
Professional Objectives (p.16)	“Professional objectives... high level of specialisation... development of professionalism... curriculum for the broadcast profession... continuous training.”	Professional Objectives & Profession Formation	NBC frames broadcasting as a profession requiring specialisation, structured training and continuous development.
Professional Standards (p.18; Programming)	“Self-regulation within the framework of professional standards.” / “Programmes must meet the best professional standards.”	Professional Standards	Professionalism is tied to high-quality output and internal enforcement of norms.
Professional Service Delivery (Intro)	“An efficient, professional broadcasting service...”	Public-Interest Professionalism	Professional practice is linked to national development and public service.
News/Emergency Reporting (p.32)	“Exercise due caution and professionalism... ensuring veracity and credibility.”	Ethical Professionalism	Professionalism involves accuracy, verification, ethical judgement and credibility.

NBC Clause (2019)	Extracted Professional Wording	Code	Interpretation
Presenter Conduct (1.10.4)	“Handle content with professionalism and sound judgment.”	Cognitive Professionalism	Professionalism requires responsible decision-making and trained judgement.
Leadership of Professional Departments (1.13.4)	“Requisite qualification and at least 10 years cognate experience... head a professional department.”	Credentialed Leadership	Leadership positions are formalised as professional posts requiring expertise and experience.
Professional Rules (Section 3.1)	“Professional Rules.”	Codified Professional Norms	NBC codifies institutional rules governing professional conduct.

Codebook for Analysing Professionalisation Constructs in the NBC (2019) Code

Definitions, inclusion criteria and examples supporting the coding of profession-related clauses

Code	Definition	Inclusion Criteria	NBC Example
Professional Objectives & Profession Formation	How NBC conceptualises broadcasting as a profession requiring specialisation, structured training, curriculum development and continuous learning.	Clauses referencing “professional objectives,” “broadcast profession,” specialisation, curriculum, or ongoing training.	“Professional objectives... curriculum for the broadcast profession... continuous training.”
Professional Standards	Expectations that programmes and practitioners must meet high-quality professional benchmarks.	Mentions of “professional standards,” “best professional standards,” or quality requirements.	“Programmes must meet the best professional standards.”
Ethical & Cognitive Professionalism	Professional behaviour involving verification, accuracy, caution, ethical responsibility and sound judgement.	Uses of “professionalism” referring to veracity, caution, credibility or presenter judgement.	“Exercise due caution and professionalism... ensuring veracity and credibility.”

Code	Definition	Inclusion Criteria	NBC Example
Credentialed Leadership	NBC’s view that leadership roles must be held by trained and experienced professionals.	Clauses referencing qualifications, cognate experience or professional departments.	“Requisite qualification and at least 10 years cognate experience...”
Codified Professional Norms	Formal rules and normative expectations that govern professional conduct.	Mentions of “professional rules,” self-regulation or codified norms.	“Professional Rules.”

Findings

Research Question One (RQ1): How does the NBC define and frame broadcast professionalisation?

Findings showed that the NBC (2019) frames broadcasting as a specialised profession grounded in structured training, curriculum development, continuous capacity building and adherence to codified professional standards. Professionalism is linked to ethical judgement, verification, accuracy, credibility, and responsible programme handling, particularly in news and emergency coverage. Leadership positions are also constructed as professional roles requiring formal qualifications and substantial cognate experience.

RQ2: What contradictions exist between the NBC’s professionalisation claims and its entry provisions?

Despite this professional framing, the Code permits entry into broadcasting with an Ordinary Diploma and allows untrained individuals to practise based on “proven aptitude,” with formal training of them deferred to two years. These permissive entry provisions directly contradict the Code’s emphasis on specialised competence, ethical responsibility, and self-regulation, creating an internal inconsistency between professional standards and recruitment requirements.

RQ3: How do these contradictions affect the competence, ethics and professional development of broadcasting?

The inconsistency between professional expectations and entry requirements weakens competence development and ethical judgement within the broadcast workforce. Allowing untrained practitioners early access to professional roles undermines effective self-regulation and limits systematic professional development. Consequently, the regulatory framework constrains the emergence of a stable and fully professional broadcast industry in Nigeria.

Discussion

The findings indicated that the Nigeria Broadcasting Code (NBC, 2019) constructs broadcasting as a specialised profession anchored in structured training, ethical judgement and codified professional standards. This framing aligns with empirical evidence showing that professionalism in broadcasting depends on formal education and systematic preparation (Adams & Sharu, 2024; Robbins & O'Connor, 2023). The emphasis of the Code on verification, accuracy, and credibility further reflects studies that link ethical discipline to public trust and professional legitimacy (Banjo & Oduwobi, 2023; Banjac, Juarez Miro & Hanusch, 2024).

Despite this convergence, the Code contradicts its professional ideals through permissive entry provisions. By approving an Ordinary Diploma and allowing aptitude-based practice prior to training, the NBC departs from evidence showing that untrained broadcasters exhibit weaker competence and ethical judgement (Adams & Sharu, 2024; Endong & Eumole, 2023; Eke, Adeyemi & Ochor, 2024). Studies also show that such practitioners are more vulnerable to commercialisation and political manipulation, further eroding professional standards (Matthews & Onyemaobi, 2020; Inobemhe, Modeyin & Ugber, 2025).

Abbott's System of Professions theory explains how these contradictions weaken professional development. Although the NBC codifies professional rules and leadership qualifications, its low entry thresholds disrupt the coherence between expertise, training, and regulation required for professional jurisdiction. This supports Kronblad & Jensen's (2023) argument that professional stability cannot be achieved where entry and training controls are weak or inconsistent.

Authoritarian Press Theory further clarifies why these inconsistencies persist. As a state-controlled regulator, the NBC retains authority over broadcasting while subordinating professional autonomy to regulatory convenience. This dynamic reflects Pearson's (2024) observation that authoritarian media systems often maintain professional rhetoric while undermining professional closure and self-regulation.

This discussion shows that empirical studies, professionalisation theory, and the NBC's stated ideals converge on the need for specialised training and ethical discipline in Nigerian broadcast sector, yet diverge in regulatory practice. Until entry standards align with the competencies prescribed in the Code, broadcast professionalisation in Nigeria will remain rhetorically strong but structurally weak.

Conclusion

Overall, the findings indicate that although the Nigeria Broadcasting Code (NBC, 2019) strongly frames broadcasting as a specialised profession grounded in structured training, ethical judgement, and codified professional standards, however, this professional vision is undermined by permissive entry provisions that allow minimally qualified or untrained individuals to practise broadcasting. The contradiction between high professional expectations and low entry thresholds weakens professional identity, constrains competence and ethical performance and limits effective self-regulation within the

Nigerian broadcast industry. Consequently, broadcast professionalisation in Nigeria remains largely aspirational, as the realisation of the NBC's professional ideals depends on aligning entry requirements with the competencies and ethical responsibilities prescribed in the Code.

Recommendations

1. The NBC should abolish provisions that allow untrained individuals to practise broadcasting in Nigeria.
2. The Commission should clearly establish a minimum academic qualification, requiring a university degree in broadcasting, journalism, or a closely related communication discipline for entry into the profession.
3. Possession of a degree certificate alone should not automatically confer the right to practise, as effective broadcasting requires practical and applied professional competence beyond academic training.
4. All new entrants into the broadcasting profession should undergo a compulsory induction and professional training programme before engaging in live broadcasting or production activities.
5. This training programme should be structured similarly to professional models such as the Nigerian Law School, ensuring standardised practical competence.
6. The training should be administered by a dedicated government institution independent of the NBC, to ensure neutrality and specialised focus.

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